

DIGITAL READING ROOMS – A NEW ERA OF ARCHIVING AND RESEARCH

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Abstract –

In the digital era, archives find themselves in an uneasy position, balancing the protection of sensitive data with the need to enable essential research using such data. The Digital Reading Room suggested in this paper uses the existing archival reading room to enable research on Restricted Access Datasets, in line with the Five Safes Framework and EU data legislation. Thus, we ensure that all safeguards are in place to fulfill the archive's task of preserving data while making it accessible for the public benefit.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Archives' *causa essendi* is the preservation, management and, above all, dissemination of information[1] [2](historical, legal or scientific) to the public. Be that digitizing paper-based records, or archiving digital born data, these processes must – even more than for analog collections - be balanced between laws and regulations, principles and ideals, and reality of what is and is not possible[3].

In this paper, we will present the idea of a Digital Reading Room (DRR), which aims to replicate the idea of trusted research environments (TRE) for archives,

on the national level at the Belgian Social Sciences and Digital Humanities Archive (SODHA[4], [5], [6], [7]). Stemming from the resources and practices of the State Archives of Belgium, our current project for a Dependable Archive for Managing Sensitive records (DAMAR [8]) will create an environment where researchers can analyze datasets containing sensitive personal data. The category of 'sensitive data' is defined extensively in Section II. Subsection 1.

Archives are increasingly responsible to ensure that data (be that historical documents, images, qualitative or quantitative surveys, to mention but a few) can be used in a safe and secure way for the public benefit. With digitization starting at the end of the last century, the role of the reading room seemed to be over in favor of online consultation. However, nothing could be further from the truth. In a digital context, the security risks do not only have a different scale but also a different dimension. Unlike analogue collections, digital data is easy to copy, increasing the risk of data misuse [9], [10]. Malware attacks can prevent researchers from accessing data essential for their research, or unintentional disclosure of personal data might violate a person's right to personal data protection and privacy. However, such data is essential for specific research into important social problems, just think of the use of medical data in the context of a pandemic. In this

context, the familiar reading room is regaining importance[11].

In sum, we will discuss the development of a DRR allowing researchers to use data containing sensitive and/or personal data for high value research.

II. LEGAL CHALLENGES

1. *Legal Aspects of Sensitive Personal Data*

Social sciences and digital humanities often rely on information about individuals, also called data subjects, within their research. Unlike data from other fields (e.g. physics, biology, etc.), the archiving and reuse of such data entails certain legal caveats.

Social scientific research frequently collects and analyzes datasets with personal data. Such data encompasses all the kinds of information through which individuals can be identified. This includes direct identifiers such as a full name or national identity number, and indirect identifiers, such as age, place of residence, etc. Indirect identifiers on their own cannot disclose the identity of a data subject, however individuals can be identified when data accumulates. While direct identifiers are not permitted in datasets deposited in SODHA, many high value datasets containing indirect identifiers should be made available for research purposes. Archiving and scientific research are examples of purposes for which personal data can be processed and reused [12],¹ if the processing is proportionate to the aim pursued [12].² Nevertheless, some personal data is more impactful for the individuals concerned, as it may open the door for discriminatory treatment or other negative effects.

Different kinds of direct or indirect personal data are considered sensitive for multiple reasons within the European legal context. Personal data is sensitive when the potential risks for the data subjects are particularly great. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) defines sensitive data as "*Personal data which are, by their nature, particularly sensitive in relation to fundamental rights and freedoms merit specific protection as the context of their processing could create significant risks to the fundamental rights and freedoms.*" [12]³

The GDPR introduces the following categories of sensitive data: (1) personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, (2) political opinions, (3) religious or philosophical beliefs, or (4) trade union membership, and (5) genetic data, (6) biometric data, (7) data concerning health or (7) data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation [12].⁴ Criminal records form a specific kind of sensitive personal data. Elaborate registers of criminal convictions can only be kept under the control of an official authority [12].⁵

2. *Restricted Access Datasets (RADs)*

A dataset may not include the names of the data subjects, but may contain a few entries with postal codes potentially from sparsely habited regions linked to religious information about individuals. Such datasets contain indirect identifiable data (residency) which falls under the aforementioned categories (religious affiliation). Similarly, gender, age, height and weight are important parts of health data, and by adding more descriptive variables (indirect identifiers) about the respondents, the chance of re-identification increases, resulting in potential disclosure of sensitive medical records. These are but two potential scenarios of many where the inclusion of one or more indirect identifiers increases the risk of disclosing sensitive information of respondents. To balance the high value of these datasets, and the need to restrict access to avoid disclosure of data subjects' personal data, both the research and the archival community needs to adopt procedures and rules, that allows responsible research on appropriate datasets for the public benefit. This categorization of RADs is in line with the approach of other data archives, such as GESIS [13] and UKDS [14]. Thereby facilitating cross-border data sharing.

3. *Legal Data Protection Obligations*

The GDPR requires these RADs to be protected through additional safeguards. For example, the processing of sensitive data is possible if national or EU law specifically requires it or if the data subject gave their explicit consent. Nevertheless, consent for the reuse of the data in a different future project by the data subject is rare. Often the future research purposes are not expected by the data depositors.

¹ Art. 89 GDPR.

² Art. 5 GDPR.

³ Recital 51 GDPR.

⁴ Art. 9 GDPR.

⁵ Art. 10 GDPR.

Moreover, consent forms an unstable ground for processing personal data, since the data subject can always retract their consent and thus render research on those datasets impossible at any moment.

If explicit consent from the data subjects is not possible, any use of sensitive data is prohibited if it is not necessary for a delineated purpose. It is complicated for archives to predict which data is strictly necessary, in particular since social scientists can have different interests in the datasets. More comprehensive ways of securing sensitive data are needed to ensure both sufficient protection and useful reuse of sensitive data.

Pseudonymization and anonymization techniques are often used to limit identifiability of data subjects. Nonetheless these techniques have shown to lack certainty as to the impossibility of re-identifying the data subjects [13], without drastically diminishing the usefulness of the dataset.

4. *Secure Access for the Public Benefit*

To counter these barriers limiting data sharing and facilitate reuse the EU recently introduced a new set of data legislation. Among them, the Data Governance Act introduced secure processing environments to enable sensitive data sharing for the public benefit, including research purposes. These environments, also called Trusted Research Environments (TREs), must grant controlled access to sensitive data while ensuring robust safeguards for security and confidentiality.

Therefore, the law sets out that the archive setting up such a secure processing environment is to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data. Where remote access is not possible without endangering rights and interests of data subjects, accessing RAD datasets can take place in the physical premises in which the secure processing environment is located [14].

III. PRACTICAL CHALLENGES

Based on the understanding of the legal requirements, we can develop clear procedures allowing access to RADs. However, the

implementation of the required infrastructure can be challenging for archives with modest budgets.

In our project, we follow the “Five Safes Framework” [15]. Therefore we must ensure that **Safe people** are conducting **Safe projects** using **Safe data** in a **Safe setting** producing **Safe outputs**. DRR could provide a Safe setting, and following the procedures of an archival reading room, we can ensure that the researchers are Safe people. By building a link between researchers and data depositors, we can provide clarity to decide what is and is not a Safe project, and our trained staff can ensure that Safe output was released from the DRR.

However, the creation of a virtual environment where we can provide data selectively for each researcher is a challenge in itself. While there are already existing solutions (see IAB⁶, GESIS⁷, UKDS⁸, etc.), the implementation is time and cost consuming. Building a system in-house takes a long time, while using a system as a service can be costly and potentially insecure. The diversity of the systems between archives further complicates the situation. To achieve its research-enhancing potential this network will have to integrate with other data providers and international partners. A potential solution is to join the International Data Access Network (IDAN) integrating systems into an international network in a trialed and tested way.

There are three major practical challenges for data archives aiming to facilitate research using RADs. First, there is the challenge of a physical infrastructure. We will tackle this challenge with the implementation of DRRs. Secondly, there is the need to scale up DRRs by creating an online network allowing researchers to remotely access RADs in a secure way. DRRs should be integrated into national and international networks. Lastly, and most importantly, these infrastructures must be maintained and the researchers assisted. To uphold the Five Safes Framework, data archives have to maintain a trained and competent staff, justifying the necessity of fundings for staff upkeep. Novel key performance indicators, such as user impact stories, and publication tracking can assist archives in this.

⁶ Institut für Arbeitsmarkt FDZ, <https://fdz.iab.de/>

⁷ GESIS, Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften, <https://www.gesis.org/home>

⁸ UK Data Service Secure Lab, <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-securelab/>

IV. PLAN OF ACTION

In this section, we elaborate on how the DAMAR project could overcome the aforementioned challenges, both legal and practical.

A. *Setting Standards for Definitions and Legal Obligations*

Concepts such as sensitive data are widely used in the archival context without national or international standards. Moreover, legal obligations must be fulfilled where RADs are processed. Thus, we started our work by defining these terms and the necessary standards to apply when facilitating research on RADs. These form the basis for developing procedures.

B. *Development of Procedures*

With a solid understanding of roles and responsibilities, we are currently developing procedures for keeping and allowing reuse of RADs. These procedures will pass three layers of testing. First, we will circulate them amongst our peers at national and international archives, since their experience can improve our work. Second, we will collect input from data depositors, on the checks and balances offered in the procedures. Lastly, we plan to engage with users, to see if the procedures are clear and understandable. These three steps ought to shape well defined, understandable, and secure procedures to facilitate research using RADs. To translate these findings and procedures into practice we will develop RAD uploading templates and events for training and knowledge exchange.

C. *Creation of the first Digital Reading Room*

Developing or implementing a cloud-based TRE is both difficult and costly. Thus, we will first create a physical safe location where researchers can conduct Safe research using RADs. The most appropriate avenue for archives is to introduce a "digital section" of the existing reading room. Thus, a first DRR will be established at the States Archive of Belgium in Brussels as a prototype for future DRRs. Building onto the established procedures for consultations of specific files by appointment, DRRs can be implemented by installing the necessary infrastructure within the existing reading room.

D. *Integrating DRRs into a Network*

The existence of a DRR will open the door for its integration as an access point into national and/or

international networks. We are currently in communication with IDAN to evaluate the possibility of joining into their international network, allowing researchers to access RAD equivalent data in France, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Germany. We will develop the settings and the procedures of the DRR in continuous communication with them, ensuring a seamless integration at a later stage.

V. CONCLUSION

In order to build a Dependable Archive for Managing Sensitive Records multiple steps have to be taken, entailing legal and practical aspects of creating a robust environment for research on sensitive data within SODHA. In this paper we provided an overview of these challenges and proposed directions towards solutions. When dealing with sensitive datasets, a clear understanding of its definition, elements and its legal implications is crucial. Therefore archives must comply with strict legal data protection and data governance rules. These rules set the scene for the potential reuse of sensitive personal data within RADs. Specifically, the implementation of a Digital Reading Room within the existing physical reading room can allow a natural development of existing analogue systems into much needed digital ones. Archival procedures are finetuned using the 5 Safes Framework to use RADs lawfully and securely be used for research. The first Digital Reading Room forms the starting point for future digital trusted research environment networks in Belgium.

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